

EFFECT OF WORK MOTIVATION AND WORK ETHICS ON TEACHER PRODUCTIVITY PRIVATE VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS IN TEBET DISTRICT SOUTH JAKARTA

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Abstract: *The purpose of this research is to know the effect of work motivation and work ethics toward Private Vocational School Teacher's productivity at Tebet Districts in South Jakarta. The research methodology was survey method with quantitative approach and path analysis technique. The population of this research is 121 teachers. Research samples is 93 teachers were selected using simple random sampling technique. The data was obtained through questionnaires and analyzed using path analysis techniques. Based on the results of the data analysis in this research, it is concluded that: (1) the work motivation has a positive direct effect to productivity; (2) the work ethics has a positive direct effect to productivity; (3) the work motivation has a positive direct effect to work ethics.*

Keywords: *Work Motivation, Work Ethic, Productivity.*

INTRODUCTION

Education can be seen as an important process to fulfill the promise of independence. Quality education will print future generations who are also qualified. This can be manifested in educational institutions.

Educational institutions are expected to be able to create the birth of intelligent leaders who are broad-minded and competent in the future. Besides educational institutions, informal education such as family also plays a role in shaping the personality of students who have noble values and good morals. So that the role of the family can also help the success of educational institutions.

In addition to school, the teacher is a determining factor in the success of students and is the spearhead in achieving educational goals. The teacher interacts with students through the learning process that is done in class. To create qualified students, the teacher is required to master 4 competencies.

Based on Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, in article 10 paragraph (1) states that: *"Teacher competencies as referred to in Article 8 include pedagogic competencies, personality competencies, social competencies, and professional competencies obtained through professional education."*

These four competencies must be owned by a teacher in order to achieve educational goals.

National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003 has said that National Education functions to develop the ability and shape of dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the life of the nation, aims to develop the potential of students to become believers and fear of God, noble, healthy, knowledgeable , capable, creative, independent, and a democratic and responsible citizen (Article 3 of the Republic of Indonesia Law No 20/2003).

The quality of Indonesian education is currently very low. Where based on data in the *Education For All (EFA) Global Monitoring Report 2011: The Hidden Crisis, Armed Conflict and Education* issued Organization of Education, Science, and Culture of the United Nations (UNESCO), which was launched in New York on Monday (1 / 3/2011), the education *development index* (EDI) based on 2008 data is 0.934. That value puts Indonesia in 69th place out of 127 countries in the world. EDI is said to be high if it reaches 0.95-1. The medium category is above 0.80, while the low category is below 0.80. While at the ASIA level, Indonesia is currently lagging behind Brunei Darussalam which is ranked 34th. Brunei was included in the high achievement group with Japan, which reached Asia's number one position. Malaysia is ranked 65th or still in the category of medium achievement groups like Indonesia. Nevertheless, Indonesia's position is still far better than the Philippines (85), Cambodia (102), India (107), and Laos (109).

The work productivity of teachers in Vocational High Schools has become a question lately, this is evidenced by the low national exam (UN) results. Overall, the average national and private vocational school level scores decreased by 4.45 points. In 2015, the average value was 62.11 while in 2016 the average value dropped to 57.66.

In addition to the problem of UN scores that have decreased, the problem is the low absorption capacity of vocational graduates in the world of work. The Ministry of Manpower noted, graduates of Vocational Schools (SMK) turned out to have low absorption rates in the world of work. In February 2017 BPS data from 131, 55 million people who entered the workforce, recorded 124, 54 million people who worked. The remaining 7.01 million people are still unemployed.

The gap between vocational school graduates and employment in employment is a problem that must be resolved by the government and the vocational school. The solution to the problem can be done by efforts to improve the quality of vocational schools, both the quality of human resources and facilities and infrastructure that support the learning process, as well as establish cooperation with employment providers.

Effectiveness is the achievement of the right goals or choosing the right goals from a series of alternatives or choice of ways and determining the choice of several other choices. Effectiveness can also be interpreted as a measure of success in achieving predetermined goals. For example if a task can be completed by selecting the methods that have been determined, then the method is correct or effective. While efficiency is the minimum use of resources to achieve optimum results.

Efficiency assumes that the correct goals have been determined and try to find the best ways to achieve these goals. Efficiency can only be evaluated by relative assessments, comparing input and output received. In other words, the task can be completed using the method correctly or efficiently.

Likewise, the effectiveness and efficiency of the teacher in learning is closely related to the competence in the form of the ability to use learning media that supports preparation and implementation of tasks as educators. Students learn from their teacher not only from what is directly taught, but also from the learning media that is seen when they are carrying out the teaching and learning process.

The problem of productivity is also still seen in private vocational schools in Tebet sub-district, South Jakarta. There are still many teachers who experience difficulties in increasing their productivity. There are still problems related to teacher productivity such as: First, there are still teachers who come late to school due to the distance between houses and schools that are relatively far away and also caused by traffic jams in Jakarta.

Secondly there are still problems related to administrative problems, completeness and readiness of teachers such as RPP. Third, the teacher's responsibility is still low in terms of teaching in class while he is present. Fourth, there were still teachers who avoided additional assignments such as being student staff, head of the expertise program, or as homeroom teacher. The teacher gives reasons that the duties and responsibilities are too heavy. Fifth, there is a school situation and climate that is not comfortable at work, and the sixth is due to delays in the payment of honorarium provided by the foundation which results in the teacher being lazy and not enthusiastic about working.

Work motivation is one of the important factors that determine the success of the teacher. The size or influence of motivation on the teacher depends on how much intensity the motivation is given. The difference in work motivation for a teacher is usually reflected in various activities and even achievements. Teacher's work motivation is a process that is carried out to move the teacher so that their behavior can be directed to real efforts to achieve the stated goals.

Teacher's work motivation has two dimensions, namely: encouragement that arises from within (internal) and encouragement arising from the outside (external). If the motivation in the school grows well in the teacher, then the motivation of his work can be realized in the form of implementation and completion of tasks that are better, more meaningful or more valuable. Conversely, the weakness of a teacher's motivation will have an impact on the lack of enthusiasm and encouragement of the teacher to carry out his duties and responsibilities in completing his work.

Common problems that often occur such as: teachers often do not enter, teachers whose teaching is not standard, teachers who are more in the office than in class and only give assignments to students, and the lack of teacher's ability to package learning media as interesting as possible increase students' interest in learning

In addition to work motivation, the teacher's work ethic is also an important factor affecting teacher productivity. Work ethics is defined as the norm of behavior that appears in a community that is part of an organization. These norms include a set of behaviors, which are generally known as work ethics, which is defined as employee loyalty to the organization, enthusiasm and pride in doing good work.

In reality there is still a negative work ethic such as complaining, demanding, selfish, working casually, lack of care, laziness, discipline, bad, low work stamina, minimal dedication, *sense of belonging* thin, lack of work passion, lack of initiative, less creative, low quality work, low serving spirit, and so on. Besides that, due to the progress of basic needs which continues to increase, the teacher must eventually have additional work.

This sideline search makes other honorary teachers / teachers absent from their main duties at school. The employees become unfocused on their work so they will be absent from their main duties and ignore their main tasks.

PRODUCTIVITY

Productivity comes from English, namely *product*, *result*, *outcome* which develops into words *productive* which means to produce, and *productivity: having the ability to make or create: creative*. From the word *productivity* it is used in Indonesian to become productivity which means strength or ability to produce something.

Stephen P. Robbins and Mary Coulter argue that "*the productivity produced by output is needed by output.*" Productivity is the output of goods or services as a whole which is produced divided by the input needed to produce the output.

This definition refers to the comparison between the amount produced by the number of each source used during production. The source can be in the form of raw materials, machinery, tools or labor.

Prokopenko states that: *productivity is the relationship between the output generated by a production or service system and the input provided to create this output. Thus, productivity is defined as efficient use of resources labor, capital, land, materials, energy, information in production of various goods and services.*

Productivity is the relationship between output / output produced by production and services and the input provided to produce output. Thus productivity is defined as the use of resources, efficient labor, capital, land, material, energy, as well as information about the types of production of goods and services.

Margareth and his friends said the cause of *low productivity* "*low productivity because individuals are not motivated to be productive*". Low productivity is caused by a lack of internal motivation to work productively.

Mary Coulter said that *employee productivity is a performance measure of both efficiency and effectiveness*. Employee productivity is a performance that can measure efficiency and effectiveness. This is "*productivity is a composite of people and operations variables. A manager should look for ways to successfully integrate people into the overall operations systems.*" Productivity is a combination of employees and their work. A manager must be able to find ways to integrate employees into the work as a whole.

Based on the description above can be synthesized work productivity is the work of someone / individual by utilizing existing resources effectively and efficiently to achieve common goals with indicators: (1) efficient use of resources, (2) utilization of resources, and (3) effectiveness of achieving goals.

WORK MOTIVATION

In relation to the work environment, Ernest J. Mc Cormick suggested that *motivation is defined as conditions which influence the arousal, direction, and maintenance of behaviors relevant in work settings*. Work motivation is defined as a condition related to generating, directing and maintaining behaviors related to the work environment.

Ruth Kanfer, Gilad Chen, and Robert D. Pitchard define: *Work motivation is commonly defined as the psychological processes that determine (or energize) the*

direction, intensity, and persistence of action within the continuing stream of experiences that characterize the person in relation to his or her work.

Work motivation is usually defined as a psychological process that determines (gives strength) the direction, intensity and perseverance in acting that is combined with the experience that someone has in relation to his work.

Furthermore Kanfer stated that: *Work motivation is a person intentions to allocate personal resources across a range of possible actions. This definition emphasizes the distributional aspect of motivation, and accounts for the critical process by which individuals exerts control over their behavior.*

Work motivation is also more precisely defined as a series of processes that determine a person's intention to allocate personal resources in various possible actions. This definition emphasizes the distribution of motivational aspects, and accounts for the critical process by which an individual is given key controls over his behavior.

The same thing was conveyed by Anderson et al. That: *Work motivation can be generally defined as a set of energetic forces that have originated within both as well as beyond an individual's being, to initiate work-related behavior, and to determine its from, direction, intensity & duration.*

Work motivation in general can be defined as a set of energetic forces that originate both inside and outside individual beings, to initiate work-related behavior, and to determine shape, direction, intensity & duration.

Based on the description of the theory above, it can be synthesized that work motivation is the drive or driving force possessed by each individual to achieve better work results with indicators: (1) working hard, (2) high enthusiasm in work (3) trying to use their abilities and (4) not feel satisfied quickly, (5) the intensity of attendance.

WORK ETHICS

David L. Goetsch: *Ethics is the right thing within a moral framework. In other words, it is the practical application of morality. What is ethical is the situation determined by applying the values that rise the prevailing moral framework.*

Ethics is about doing the right thing in a moral framework. In other words, it is a practical application of morality. What is ethical in certain situations is determined by applying values that consist of a valid moral framework.

According to Robert P. Vecchio stated that: *Work ethic embodies a set of beliefs, including a belief in the dignity of all work, contemplating for idleness and self-indulgence, and a belief that if you work hard, you will be rewarded. When asked to perform simple, dull and repetitive tasks without financial incentives, endorses of work ethic are more persistent and productive.*

Work ethics puts confidence, which includes a dignified belief from all occupations, does not like laziness and self-participation, and the belief that if you work hard you will be rewarded.

Work ethic is "a set of values based on hard work and diligence". Work ethics is a set of values based on hard work and crafts. This also means a trust in the benefits of work morale and its ability to improve its character including trustworthiness, initiative or maintenance of social abilities.

John W. Newstrom, Keith Davis stated that: *The work ethic for many years of the culture of the western world has emphasized work as a desirable and fulfilling activity.*

The cultural emphasis is work ethic for many people, meaning that they view work as very important and as an desired goal in life. They tend to like work and derive satisfaction from it. They usually have a stronger commitment to the organization and to its goals than do other employees.

Over the years work ethic in the western world has become a force that confirms that work ethics is an activity that is desired and is a necessity. The result of this cultural concern is work ethics for many people, has an understanding that they view work ethics as something very important and a desirable goal in their lives, while maintaining and liking work to obtain job satisfaction and usually have a strong commitment to the organization and on the goals of the organization.

Laurie J. Mullins said that, *"the work ethic prevails, implying heads down works, focused agendas, punctuality, efficiency"*. Work ethics applies, including work, focusing on the agenda, timeliness, and efficiency.

From the description above can be synthesized work ethics is a person's behavior in carrying out his work based on moral and good behavior that shows professional work, with indicators as follows: 1) full of accuracy, 2) appreciate work time, 3) hard work, 4) prioritize work results and 5) building employment relationships.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was carried out in the PRIVATE VOCATIONAL SCHOOL OF KECAMATAN TEBET JAKARTA SELATAN which was carried out for 3 (three) months. The method used in this study is a survey using causal techniques. The population in this study was a teacher of 121 people, with a sample of 93 teachers, the data collected in this study were nets through questionnaires in the form of *rating scales* with a distribution of scores between 1 and 5. After descriptive analysis continued with analysis requirements test in the form of analysis requirements test in the form of normality test, data linearity test and regression significance, hypothesis testing is done using path analysis techniques (*path analysis*)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE EFFECT OF WORK MOTIVATION ON PRODUCTIVITY

From the results of testing the first hypothesis it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence on Work Motivation on Productivity with a correlation coefficient of 0.550 and a path coefficient of 0.385. This gives the meaning of Work Motivation has a direct positive effect on Productivity.

The results of this study are in line with the opinions of several experts including Laurence explaining the influence of motivation on work productivity as follows; *Stimulated by Japanese competitors, managers in car production and the machine construction industry started in the beginning of this decade to introduce the group work in combination with efforts to improve productivity. One of the reasons they have in mind for a change in work organization, from individual to group organization, was to design conditions for a better work motivation of their organizational members. They are perceived work motivation as an influential factor for increasing flexibility and productivity of work.*

Stimulated by competitors from Japan, managers in the machinery construction and car production industries began at the beginning of this decade introducing group work combined with high effort to increase productivity. One of the reasons they change work organizations, from individual organizations to group organizations is to design circumstances to produce better work motivation from members. They assume that work motivation is a factor that influences increased flexibility and work productivity.

Furthermore Don Hellriegel also explained the view that; *Motivation represents the forces acting on or within a person that causes the person to behave in a specific, goal directed manner. Because the motives of employees affect their productivity, one of management's jobs is to channel employee motivation affectively toward achieving organizational goals. However, motivation isn't the same as performance. The most highly motivated employees may not be successful in their jobs, especially if they don't have the competencies needed to perform the jobs or they work under unfavorable job conditions. Although job performance involves more than motivation, motivation is an important factor in achieving high performance.*

Motivation produces strength that acts above or within a person that causes the person to have a clear and purposeful goal. Because management motivation is directing the motivation of employees who have high motivation may not be the same as performance. Even employees who have high motivation can be unsuccessful at work, especially if they have the competencies needed to do the job or they work under unfavorable working conditions. Although job performance is more involved than motivation, motivation is still an important factor in improving higher performance.

The same thing was explained by Colquitt that; *One way of judging the motivational impact of the plan is to provide difficult and specific goals, because both challenges to employees next to year are good (on better) than this year. In contrast, lump sum bonus and gang sharing provide a forum for assigning difficult and specific goals; the former does at the individual level and the latter at the unit level. Party for this season, both types of plans have been credited with improvement in employee productivity.*

One way of assessing the motivational impact of the element of the compensation plan is to consider whether the element is able to set specific and difficult goals to channel the work effort. Appropriate revenue sharing and payment systems provide little motivation related to specifying specific and difficult goals, because in essence both (the system for payment and appropriate payments) give employees the challenge to make next year as good or even better than this year. Instead bonus futures and group-based profit sharing systems provide space for setting specific and difficult goals; where the first money works at the individual level and second at the individual level and second at the unit or group level.

The conclusion is that the two types of plans that have been mentioned are believed to be able to increase employee productivity. Based on the statement above, work motivation has a direct positive effect on productivity.

EFFECT OF WORK ETHICS ON PRODUCTIVITY

From the results of the testing of the third hypothesis it can be concluded that there is a positive direct influence of Work Ethics on Productivity with a correlation coefficient of 0.542 and a path coefficient of 0.370. This gives the meaning of Work Ethics has a direct positive effect on Productivity.

The results of this study are in line with the opinions of several experts including Barton H. Hamilton, Jack A. Nickerson, and Hideo Owan in his journal entitled "Work Ethics and Workers' Diversity: An Empirical Analysis of Team Impacts on Productivity".

This study focused on being a reinforcing reference regarding the effect of work ethics on productivity: *Effect of ethics against output and average average productivity increased when the specific members work in teams. Productivity increased taxable income consistent implementation team with predictions. Utilization collaboration and skills, but also can be compromised and exemplifies lesson together, where will result balance of any member of its members.*

The influence of ethics on output and the average productivity of certain members increases when working in teams. Productivity increases after team implementation is consistent with predictions that not only utilize collaboration and skills but can also compromise and exemplify mutual teaching, which will lead to a balance of each member's ideas.

Organizations that have been successful with the team, including increased productivity, improved quality, greater innovation, and higher member satisfaction by supporting the idea that the team provides benefits to members and organizations. But if it is only regulating members into the team does not guarantee the effectiveness. Managers are responsible for creating and maintaining conditions and processes that allow the team to be successful.

The team should consist of people who have different productivity and expertise so that they can coordinate and cooperate with leaders. For that reason, utilizing the diversity of skills possessed by each individual is not enough, meaning that there is a need to balance or harmonize the work model with ideas or ideas from members of the organization. Therefore, in a team there is a strong interdependence with each other to achieve a goal in completing a task.

With the existence of work ethics, the results are expected to exceed the target to be achieved compared to when done individually. If it is related to the results, the influence of the work team on the productivity of members is closely related.

Furthermore Joseph J. Martocchion stated the positive impact of work ethics on productivity: *Organizations are concerned about achieving a potentially diverse set of outcomes, including productively, cost control, innovation, learning and working morale. Research on work ethic provides insight into how to work ethically to achieve these different outcomes. For example, recent research has shown that work ethics features such as environment and teams can have positive impact on organizational productivity.*

A good organization focuses on achieving diverse potential, including productivity, cost control, innovation, learning, and teacher morale. Research on work ethics provides insight into how ethics can achieve different outcomes. For example, recent research shows that work ethic features such as the environment and team can have a positive impact on organizational productivity.

Then Michael A. West in his book entitled Effective Team Work explains the impact of work ethics on productivity, *"the influence of team-based work and productivity will improve the quality of its members. The positive effects of teamwork will bring productivity diverse.* The influence between team-based work and productivity will improve the quality of its members. The positive effects of teamwork will lead to diverse productivity.

Based on the description stated above, the work ethic has a direct positive effect on productivity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings that have been discussed in CHAPTER IV, it can be obtained some conclusions as follows: **(1)** Productivity is directly influenced positively by work motivation. This means that the increase in work motivation results in an increase in productivity in private vocational school teachers in Tebet Sub-district, South Jakarta, **(2)** Productivity is directly influenced positively by work ethics. This means, that an increase in work ethics results in productivity in private vocational school teachers in Tebet Subdistrict.

(3) Work ethics are directly influenced positively by work motivation. This means that an increase in work motivation results in an increase in work ethics for teachers in the private vocational school in Tebet, South Jakarta.

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